

Application of educational technology for promoting quality of teacher education

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ABSTRACT:

Teaching is a noble profession. Teachers are social engineers and instruments to mold our adolescent learners according to the needs and aspirations of the society. But upgrading of knowledge on the part of teachers is the primary concern to maintain the top position in professional development capacity building in the society. The researcher found positive impact of educational technology on teacher education. Researchers conduct research on enhancing the teaching learning process, improving teacher competencies, promoting research and innovation, professional development of teachers, evaluation and assessment, administrative and management efficiency. Key words: Technology, teacher education, teaching.

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Introduction:

According to Jack Podujil "I am a teacher. It is the greatest gift that life can give me, because I am allowed to spend my days with the future of the world. My students will be presidents, doctors, lawyers and craftsmen; but hopefully they will all be teachers of some kind". Teaching is a noble profession. Teachers are social engineers and instrumental in shaping our adolescent students according to the needs and aspirations of the society. But professional development capacity building, upgradation of knowledge from teachers is the primary concern to maintain the highest status in the society.

Educational technology plays an important role in transforming teacher education in the 21st century. It refers to the systematic use of technology, digital tools and innovative methods to improve teaching, learning and assessment processes. In teacher education, educational technology helps develop competent, reflective and technically skilled teachers who can meet the demands of the modern classroom.

Enhancing teaching learning process:

The use of digital tools like as Interactive Smart Board/ Digital Board, Projector, Computer/ Laptop/ Tablet, Document camera/ visualizer, High-speed Internet Connection, Audio system, Web camera, Digital attendance, etc. in the classroom makes the teaching learning process easier and more efficient. Through the use of the digital board, the teacher can update any new information and search and say, as well as play videos with the content. Through the projector, the teacher presents the content in front of the students through power point presentation, through which important information can be presented through diagrams along with the content explanation. By using biometrics, attendance of students is ensured through digital attendance and there is no scope for bias. Communication with all the students within the classroom is facilitated through the use of audio system. Through high-speed internet connection it is possible to teach students online along with face-to-face interaction in the teacher's classroom. With video recording, if a student is absent from the class, he can later watch the video to catch up with the class. Synchronous and asynchronous learning is possible through the internet. During synchronous learning, the teacher interacts virtually face-to-face with the students and can solve the doubts of the students. But asynchronous learning does not have this opportunity, but students can access the course materials and learn at their own time.

Improving teacher competencies:

For skill development of trainee teachers, video recording is arranged through the use of technological devices during microteaching through which students can later identify their weaknesses through video analysis and the supervisor guides them for improvement. Through reflective teaching the teacher can evaluate himself and technology is also very important in this evaluation. Pre-service teacher education provides an opportunity to practice in a virtual classroom before going to a real classroom. In the modern age teaching profession a teacher needs to be proficient in the proper use of technological tools in all aspects of teaching-learning situation, teacher-student interaction classroom and management. The teacher should have proper

knowledge about data storage, maintaining privacy, digital awareness through which he will develop awareness among the students because in the present time human life is not possible without technology. Through this awareness it will be possible to control the bad effects of technology among students.

Professional development of teachers:

For professional development of in-service teachers, they can take skill development courses like online training courses, webinars, online workshops etc. at home. Organizations like NCTE, IGNOU, NITTTR, SWAYAM etc. conduct various online courses on teacher education, which teachers can study themselves for updating and skill development. Through technology, teachers can connect with education related communities in the world using various tools like Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, Zoom, etc. The technology introduces teachers to modern teaching methods, such as blended learning, flipped classrooms, and gamified learning. Through technology, teachers can easily adopt a culture of continuous professional development and teachers can stay updated with new curriculum changes, policies, and educational research through online communities and platforms.

Evaluation and assessment:

The use of technology in evaluation and assessment makes it more accurate, flexible, transparent and learner centered. Teacher educators use various online platforms such as Google Forms, Kahoot, Mentimeter, Quizizz, etc. to instantly understand students. Scoring using these tools makes the scores more objective and reliable and bias does not affect the scores. Digital portfolios, E-assessment, Online Quiz, etc. are used for continuous assessment. Through this, the weakness of the students can be easily identified and attempts are made to solve their problems through remedial teaching. Through this the progress of the students can be tracked accurately. Create digital portfolio for student teacher self-evaluation including showcasing lesson plans, teaching videos and reflections. Computer based testing is used to assess students' proficiency through standardized tests for admission. When students go out to practicals such as school-based activity, community-based activity, visit of historical place etc. Their transparency is evidenced by taking photos with location.

Administrative and management efficiency:

Teacher education institutions in India are run by NCTE and University. When NCTE formulate policies and rules for teacher education, they can be easily enforced by the institutions. After implementing the policies, NCTE collects online data from institutions to evaluate the implementation effects of the policies. Administrative track can be easily done by uploading documents online to check whether the institutions are following the correct rules. Attendance of students and teachers can be verified easily through biometric system. The problem of poor communication between NCTE, university and institutions has been solved through technology. There is no need to be in physical attendance to discuss any matter, it is possible to have virtual attendance through Google Meet, Zoom, etc. As a result, the cost of time and money is reduced. This enhances maintenance, reduces unnecessary efforts, minimizes storage place and lessons security risks.

Promoting research and innovation:

Through the use of technology, the teacher will be aware of global educational trends as well as gain knowledge about the various results of research on teacher education. Use technological tools such as SPSS, Online Survey Platforms, Excel, etc. for research work. By using them, the teacher can do data analysis in less time as well as its accuracy is much higher. Surveys through online survey platforms can be done in less time, less cost and data collection at home. To collect information about a subject, the teacher can access data from the E-journal, Digital library at any time and any place. In the current education system, emphasis is placed on inclusive education, and technology is playing an important role in this inclusive education, such as skin reading, audio books, audio recording use for the visually impaired students.

Conclusion:

The use of digital tools like as Interactive Smart Board/ Digital Board, Projector, Computer/ Laptop/ Tablet, Document camera/ visualizer, High-speed Internet Connection, Audio system, Web camera, Digital attendance, etc. in the classroom makes the teaching learning process easier and more efficient. The teacher can evaluate himself through reflective teaching and technology is also very important in this evaluation. Organizations such as NCTE, IGNOU, NITTTR, SWAYAM, etc. conduct various online course on teacher education which teachers can study themselves for updating and skill development. The use of technology in evaluation and assessment makes it more accurate, flexible, transparent and learner centered. Teacher educators use various online platforms such as Google Forms, Kahoot, Mentimeter, Quizizz, etc. to instantly understand students. The researcher find out positive impact of educational technology on teacher education, basically enhancing teaching learning process, improving teacher competencies, promoting research and innovation, professional development of teachers, evaluation and assessment.

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